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“MY DOLL IN 2015”

I once found this little toy doll; quiet, and daunting,
I named her C.
Her face is handsome, though not modern,
What a bright smile she has!
Yet, I avoid looking through her eyes,
Afraid that she might read my soul.

When I am alone, she accompanies me without complaints.
I couldn't understand how she did it.
We spend cold nights together and tell each other's lives,
She speaks to me like she knows my language.

“She's mine!” I whisper, again and again.
I screamed, I found her! Tucked away in a box marked C3.

While playing with her, I feel a pang inside me,
Because I know someone might own her.
Yet in my hands, she trembles like an old melody.
Yes, she sings! And speaks without a sound!
A song that remembers voices before mine.

Could she be longing for hands long gone?
A voice inside me says “Leave her alone, return her”.
Indeed, she must belong to the echoes of yesterday,
Concealing sorrow beneath her stare while we play.
One day, I bravely asked, with a brittle voice,
“Is there someone owning you”? She replied
with confidence, “NO. I only have you”!

Could it be truth? Or a beautiful lie?
With my patient hands, didn't I
comb her hair when it was messy?
Wasn't I generous enough, breathing life into her lonely world?

But life is cruel in its silent truths.
What is borrowed cannot be kept,
no matter how tightly we hold on.
With falling tears, and trembling fingers,
I return her, to the arms of her yesterday.

Now, I ache to hold her and play with her again,
To hear the lullabies she once sang for me.
But against the cold toy shop's windows,
to my aching heart;
"I could buy another, couldn't I? One that is mine.
No songs of yesterday, untouched, unknown,
One that has only me- Truly Mine.

Could I?"